

2025 Brian Raess Family Halloween Message

Greetings from Mexico! Mayte, Paul and I have been doing well this year, with Paul graduating from University in Puebla on June 12th. He sent us wonderful video. Reminds me of the days when I donned the 'ol cap & gown. He thereafter visited us in Durango, and helped me capture some images of our family photos. In July, Mayte and I celebrated our 25th Wedding Anniversary, also known as the Silver Anniversary. Our beloved pets (cats Nieve, Candy, Sabrina, & dog Boni) are well-cared for and content at home, often sprawling out on our beds, 'comfy' as can be.

In Summer, Paul headed to El Paso, and then caught a flight to Chicago with his family, where they visited the Willis Tower as well as the Shedd Aquarium. They are having fun in the 'Windy City.' Paul got hired by a couple of jobs and has been steadily employed. Like I told Garret, 'he's just a chip off the old block!' Mayte and sisters also raced to Mazatlan in July, pouring onto its beaches like Bacchanales with a vengeance!

Tragedy struck the family earlier this year, when Jesus' step-sister, a young woman, was killed in a bus accident, when a truck struck a passenger bus on a highway near Cuencamé, Durango, Mexico, causing about fourteen deaths. She had been visiting from Texas.

Also, I learned of the passing of my cousin, Catholic nun Sr. Elizabeth Anne Swartz, SSND- who was also the Swartz family historian. She gently corrected some of my initial confusion about grandma Margaret's siblings and helped me 'catch the bug' so to speak. May she rest with the angels.

We also mourn the 'Black Swan' event of so many lives lost during the floods that struck Texans along the Guadalupe River on July 4th weekend and other regions as well, which resulted in catastrophic results. We mourn the loss of so many young lives, and praise the brave adults who mustered the courage to try and save so many. They surely could have used 'Noah's Ark' during this event!

We support U.S. foreign policy in the Middle East and continued military & economic support to Isreal. We pray for the lessening of civilian casualties in Gaza. We don't know what the result of Pres. Trump's foreign policy will be- Utopia or Apocalypse? – but it is certainly interesting to watch as it unfolds. We praise our brave U.S. troops for 'doing the job' in Iran, Isreal, Yemen and elsewhere worldwide.

We support Ukraine in its existential struggle with Russia, as well as the continued flow of western military & economic aid to Ukraine. I continue to back the activities of American Veterans for Ukraine (AVU).

Therefore, we pray for Peace in the World and Goodwill among Mankind!

God Bless You & God Bless America!

Brian & Family